

Impact Factor: 8.67

ISSN:0976-8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

Bi-Monthly Peer-Reviewed eJournal

16 YEARS OF OPEN ACCESS

VOL. 16 ISSUE-3, JUNE 2025

Editor-In-Chief: **Dr. Vishwanath Bite**
Managing Editor: **Dr. Madhuri Bite**

www.the-criterion.com

AboutUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/about/>

Archive: <http://www.the-criterion.com/archive/>

ContactUs: <http://www.the-criterion.com/contact/>

EditorialBoard: <http://www.the-criterion.com/editorial-board/>

Submission: <http://www.the-criterion.com/submission/>

FAQ: <http://www.the-criterion.com/fa/>

ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

Linguistic Variables in a Multilingual and Multicultural World

Dr. Leena Sarkar Bhaduri

Assistant Professor,
Department of English,
Shree Agrasen Mahavidyalaya, Dalkhola,
Uttar Dinajpur, West Bengal.
Affiliated to University of Gour Banga.

Article History: Submitted-21/05/2025, Revised-15/06/2025, Accepted-23/06/2025, Published-30/06/2025.

Abstract:

We live in a multicultural and bilingual environment. L1 (our native language) & L2 (second language) exists together in the linguistic resources that consistently supports the system that helps every bilingual speaker to survive in the world. A number of studies have documented the cognitive outcomes associated with bilingualism. Some studies have also focused on the effect of bi/multilingualism on verbal intelligence that involves understanding of language and its effective usage and the effect on non-verbal intelligence which focuses on analytical skill with the help of paralinguistics without involving any language in it. However, the bridge between L1 and L2 is still under construction because unlike the signified picture which the sound-image 'bridge' compels us to visualize, this 'bridge' remains transcendental to the sensory details as it is non-linear and works on multiple levels of human comprehension. The attempt in this paper is to bring out the correlation between bilingualism and the diversity in the linguistic domain. It also attempts to focus on the impact of Whorfianism on verbal and non-verbal communication in bi/pluri-lingual domains.

Keywords: Bilingualism, Monolingualism, Multiculturalism, Whorfianism.

Introduction

Language is the essential disciplines that can extend its help towards overcoming challenges in every domain. The guidance of language and the proper understanding of language inspire us, change our perception and build new ideas that are required to support our existence in this multicultural and multidimensional world. The process of communication is mutating rapidly with the evolution. The pigeon has long been transformed into mail and voices of the subjugated shifted our focus from mono-lingualism to bi/ pluri- lingual domains. According to Uriel Weinrich bilingualism is “the practice of using two languages simultaneously”. (Weinrich, 1953) In the words of Diebold it is “the ability to use two languages in the environment of the native language”. (Diebold, 1964) Bloomfield claims that a bilingual should be competent enough to have “native like control of two or more languages”. (Bloomfield, 1933) We can also consider it as speech communities where several languages coexist to make the communication effective among large groups of people. The concept of Speech Community however suspends an individual’s belief in one single community guided by only one language and no sense of respect for other languages This equation in any community is considered very undemocratic and brings in inequalities among other groups of people. In a broader context we can think in a different way-each speech community acts as a social aggregate and should have equal space for other languages. Only then there can be social equality and camaraderie among everyone living in the society. A lot of research has already been done with the concept of bilingualism. A number of studies have documented the cognitive outcomes associated with bilingualism. Some studies have also focused on the effect of bilingualism on verbal and non-verbal intelligence. However,

the gap between L1 and L2 is still under construction because unlike the signified picture which the sound-image ‘bridge’ compels us to visualize, this ‘bridge’ remains transcendental to the sensory details as it is non-linear and works on multiple levels of human comprehension. It is evident that there are potential relationships between bilingualism and linguistic variables.

It is generally accepted that in an ELT classroom L1 is English and all other vernacular and regional languages stand as L2. However, the aspects and avenues of the Lx-Ly/L1-L2 relationship do not remain constant all the time. Perhaps Chomsky’s idea of the LAD or Language Acquisition Device would help us to comprehend the situation better. In 1960, Noam Chomsky came up with a theory that an individual is born with some innate facilities or attributes which helps him/her to understand language in future. This theory discards the earlier one that one’s mind is like a blank page and installs a new idea that mind is not blank; it is already pre-programmed to understand language. Chomsky does not agree with the belief that children learn language by imitating and blindly following their adults instead he proposed the concept of Language Acquisition Device. It is considered to be a hypothetical tool that helps children to learn language. According to the theory all human languages have a common syntactical pattern which children biologically inherit from their parents and thereby acquire it easily as they grow up. They receive the input in their brain and with that biological direction they are able to frame grammatically correct sentence. In the words to Chomsky LAD is a special trait which only humans can adapt. The difficulties and ambiguities of grammar and syntax are configured in human brain which helps in the acquisition of language.

Methodology

As defined by Clark: “Language is not an autonomous system for communication. It is embedded in and supplemented by gesture, gaze, stance, facial expression, voice quality in the full array of options people can use for communicating.” (Clark, 2009). Learning becomes complicated as it is associated with the context and the culture. It is also influenced by our versatile experiences as we humans always come across various circumstances which directly and indirectly influence us and guide us in every possible way. Now let us consider a scenario. In an ELT classroom, the teacher tries to establish communication in L1 or English. For him, English becomes the language of thought and expression in the classroom. However, the students, as non-native English speakers, try to express himself/herself in English while the process of comprehension goes on in vernacular. Generally, he/she would try to process the words of the teacher through vernacular and in this regard for that particular student, at the time of communication, vernacular becomes L1 while English, the language of expression, remains L2. The relationship of L1-L2 is often conceived in various independent versions by both the teacher and the students, especially during the time of verbal communication.

Let us consider another scenario. In a movie named ‘Arrival’, Aliens arrive on earth and unlike the popular myths, they want to communicate. Authorities summon a linguist to decipher the language, because again unlike the popular myths, verbal communication fails. With many trials and months of hard work, she finds a way to translate their gestures into language with the help of sign- language, as, like human written communication, the aliens too have symbols to represent their thought. She becomes the first human to communicate with them through their language and prevents conflict. However, the movie doesn’t end here. She starts dreaming glimpses of her past and future life as a result of immersion, her dreams remain normal, but they

are non-linear, as she is dreaming in their language. In another movie “Shakha Proshakha” (Branches of the Tree), directed by Satyajit Ray, we come across a character who only expresses his emotions through gestures. In the plot of the movie, the second son Proshanto, a promising and successful minerologist based in London meets with an accident and finally comes back to stay with his father Anandamohan Majumdar, an affluent industrialist who always led life of honesty and sincerity. In this movie also Proshanto is unable to speak in normal human language after his accident and he is comprehended only by his father. His happiness and displeasure have only one mode of communication and that is gesture and facial expression. The twist in the movie comes when the astute, honest industrialist Mr. Annandamohan Majumdar comes to know about the corruption and dishonesty practiced by his two sons Prabodh and Probir. When Proshanto comes to know about the fact he expresses his displeasure by banging the table when everyone sits for dinner. His language is comprehended only by his father and he gradually takes him away to his room. In this way it is observed in the movie that the sign language of Proshanto could be deciphered only by his father and by no one else. Finally, we see the aged patriarch is left behind with his son Proshnato while everyone else leaves for their destination. Paralinguistics plays a significant role as the movie criticizes the vices of the society and the protest is depicted not only with the help of verbal repertoire; sign language plays a crucial role to highlight the theme deeply embedded in the story line. The Linguist’s condition may be better interpreted with the help of ‘*Sapir- Whorf Hypothesis*’. Linguist Edward Sapir and his student Benjamin Lee Whorf are known for their contribution in the popularization of this very principle. Their collective theory, known as the Sapir-Whorf Hypothesis or more commonly the Theory of Linguistic Relativity, plays a very significant role in understanding and developing communication theory as a whole. Linguistic Relativity states that “structural differences

between languages will be paralleled by nonlinguistic cognitive differences in the native speakers of the two languages.” (Brown, 1976). In simple terms people who communicate with the help of different languages or who are multilingual, perceive and think about the entire world in a versatile way as the structural diversity of languages is not parochial, it is infinite. Another theory postulated by Sapir and Whorf is “Linguistic Determinism which states that “the structure of a language strongly influences or fully determines the way its native speakers perceive and reason about the world.” (Brown, 1976). So, in simple terms linguistic determinism also states that our thought process is determined by language. The theory also fulfills the conditions, which essentially determine its functionality. The Theory of Linguistic Relativity also holds that: one’s language shapes one’s view of reality. It is a *mould* theory in that it “represents language as a mould in terms of which thought categories are cast”. (Chandler, 2002) The theory also states that the grammatical framework or the syntax of a language has a great impact on the modes of thought and behavioral characteristic of the culture in which it is articulated, thus, while the linguist finds a way to communicate to the aliens, her own perception and worldview goes through a complete metamorphosis and she starts dreaming in their language, irrespective of the presence of her own L1. The movie, ‘Arrival’ shows that the process of communication is not linear and feedback works on multiple layers of interpretation. It is also observed in the movie “Shakha Proshakha” (Branches of the Tree), where Proshanto’s behaviour or non-verbal communication can be deciphered only by his father but not by anyone else. Only by understanding his vision, his father could understand the agony of his soul when he realizes that his elder brothers are dishonest and they indulge in corruption to amass wealth. Only Anandamohan Majumdar’s interpretation of the sign language of Proshanto gives a new dimension to the movie. The movie ends with the three words “Shanti, Shanti, Shanti” which

means (peace) and Anandamohan Majumdar utters this by holding the hands of Proshanto where communication is non-linear as there is only visual representation of feelings and the feedback between the sender and receiver is interpreted at different layers. Thus, Linguist Ferruccio Rossi Landi states “that the formal relationships of language exert an influence on the rest of social life and on the way of thinking of the speaker of that language” (Language As Work & Trade, 1983).

The movie, “Arrival” shows us another important aspect of communication. It shows that the reason behind the failure of verbal communication is the presence of sound-image. Human verbal communication uses distinct sound-images which are attached to the world around us. For example, when we say ‘Table’, we tend to focus on a distinct object and the persons spoken to also conceive the same image while relating or replying. However, in the movie, ‘Aliens’ language is seismographic or the sign-language; it conveys meaning without representing sound. In the words of Powell Barry, it is also defined as “written symbols and languages that are not based on spoken words. It predated the advent of the creation of the language-based writing system.” (Barry, 2012) For this reason, they failed to communicate as the medium of human verbal communication opened up a second communication channel to them. The linguist though, understood this problem and bridged the gap with the help of sign language, establishing a meaningful signifier-signified relationship. With her instruction, a man would walk and on a nearby signboard the activity signified (walking in this case) would be written. Aliens mimed the activity and came up with a symbol which would signify the same activity in their language. Very soon, the linguist came up with a glossary of symbols, like a thesaurus to communicate to the aliens in their language. In the movie “Shakha Proshakha” (Branches of the Tree), the sign – language of Proshanto dominates the entire movie. Although there is verbal communication but the social message is conveyed through the underlying meaning of the sign language. Here

Anandamohan Majumdar finally expresses his desire to stay in peace only with Proshanto where the mode of communication is through sign-language. He could easily communicate with him in his language with the help of symbols thereby establishing beautifully the signifier-signified relationship.

Now, if we consider a multicultural ELT classroom, we may witness the failure of verbal communication with a student from vernacular medium at the moment of first contact. There will be fear, hesitation and other relevant factors affecting the communication process. In an ELT classroom student who belong to the category of First-Generation Learner, seldom reciprocate. There is extreme paranoia of failure and their only mode of communication is through sign language. The facilitator needs to comprehend their body language so that he/she may progress in class and also to maintain harmony among everyone. This situation is not so different from the scenario in the movie at the first attempt to establish communication with the aliens or in the other movie under consideration where Proshanto is unable to speak and can communicate only through facial expression and sign - language. The presence of sound-image perhaps creates a problem for both the teacher and learner because of the variations of cultural and linguistic barrier as well as pronunciation. A Marathi or a Telegu student may not utter and comprehend 'Table' in the same way a student from West Bengal does. However, the sign for table remains same for both.

Discussion

Therefore, we may deduce that at the moment of establishing communication at the initial stage with a student, who is a non-native English speaker, we may take recourse to sign language to make an effective communication. In this way, the student will feel more comfortable and due to

the synthesis of the communication channels the learning process will also be reinforced. However we have considered our assumptions from the perspective of the multilingual world and we incidentally have come across some perceptible challenges of bilingualism in a multicultural world, which also plays a very decisive role in positing our framework of understanding the linguistic variables. The challenges are:

- a) L1 and L2, due to inter-dependence, may undergo certain changes at the level of sound, syntax, vocabulary and semantics. In Indian context the effect of this is perceived as MTI. India is a multilingual country and for the predominance of L1 or native language in our life, it tends to influence the phonological structure we follow for L2. Mother Tongue influence (MTI) is a terrible threat to a multicultural work environment, where business out sourcing is a phenomenon encompassing the entire world and its work culture.
- b) Another popular threat to the speech community is the degree of importance we offer on L1 and L2. Due to various socio-cultural and historical factors, one language may be considered as the language of education, social interaction and for professional excellence and the other language may not be looked at with same dignity and intellectual acceptance. In the context of India, L1 is the native language of the individual province and L2 is primarily English. In a progressive and globalised country, it is obvious that L2 is considered to be official language for all communication and L1 for social and emotional communication where perception is involved and not professional exuberance.

- c) Another potential challenge is the concept of ‘Code-mixing’ and ‘Code-switching’. There is a tendency to use L1 and L2 in different realms and circumstances. ‘Code Switching’ is a common factor interfering the regular life of all bilingual speakers. It is observed in psycholinguistic research, that overlapping of languages is a common phenomenon in the speech community of all bi/multilingual speech community. It is quite difficult to completely erase or put down the effect of one language over the other in any linguistic domain. Such switching is quite vulnerable as it may or may not be accepted in a speech community. In a very traditional work environment, the occasional ‘code-mixing’ and ‘code-switching’ may lead to confusion. However, in a very modern and progressive work culture, where people from all strata with high academic credentials and intellectual pursuit struggle to achieve something great; this gets wide currency and approval.
- d) If in an academic environment, both L1 and L2 are given equal importance and credit, then it can become an unwanted pressure on the student. It is highly debatable but in this competitive environment students want to focus more on what they aspire to achieve in life than giving equal importance to all the languages in their academic life. It is obvious that students who are passionate and have love for language may give equal thrust to L1 and L2 but the same can never be applicable for all. In Indian context L2 is considered as language of high dignity and social recognition, thereby leading to negative impact on speakers of L1 community. It is a social construct which has no concrete foundation rather a concocted story that prevails on human mind generation after generation. In this era every child accepts L2 more than L1 as L2 is getting priority in our life for professional competence in this competitive market. In such a situation there is a

complete or partial loss of L1. As a result of this vernacular language is gradually losing its relevance in several speech communities.

Conclusion

So, from this analysis we can deduce that the research is applicable in all types of lingual domains. The objective of this paper is to focus on the webbed impact of linguistic variables on multilingual/multicultural domains. In today's world an individual (native and non-native both) is bound to face barriers/challenges while using verbal communication. The research of Prof Mehrabian shows that the comprehension process of a verbal message consists of certain percentages, 7% of meaning in the words that are spoken, 38% of meaning is paralinguistic (the way that the words are said), and 55% of meaning is in facial expression. So, the essence of the message may disappear in our attempt to register. The reference of the movie "Arrival" is significant in this regard, where the aliens fail to obtain meaning from the human-spoken-words. It is also same with the reference of the movie "Shakha Proshakha" (Branches of the Tree) where Proshanto is unable to communicate to his brothers (representatives of the civilized human world) as they are more inclined to build their future using malpractice and dishonesty. Proshanto, could communicate with music as music is shown as his passion and he could also communicate with his father who could easily understand his sign and signals. The situation is more critical in an ELT classroom, where culture and social background sometimes play a significant role in the language acquisition of the first-generation learners. A teacher's attempt to establish an effective communication channel is often nullified due to the nuanced effect of translation. There is a common phenomenon observed among the first-generation learners and that is translation. They tend to translate everything from L1 to L2 and not even trying to imagine, speak and develop their thought process in L2. The ambience is another factor in a

student's learning and in some cases an enforced process of language-teaching may create adverse effects, while debilitating the learner's process of acceptance. However, if the bilingual or multilingual speaker at first takes the help of the sign language to understand the concept and thereby to reciprocate, then perhaps the barriers faced by him/her would be less in number and it would also make the process of interaction interesting with a glossary of words (signifiers), giving meaning to each distinct sign (signified). This paper therefore tries to explore the multifarious arenas of lingual domains with a focus to the variables that shape our perception, while advocating the influence/inclusion of sign language to make the process of learning effective and reinforced.

Works Cited:

Baker C. *Key Issues in Bilingualism and Bilingual Education*. United Kingdom, Clevedon: Multilingual Matters, 1988.

Bloomfield L. *Language*. New York, New York: Holt, 1933.

Brown H. Douglas, *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching*. United States of America ,Pearson Education, 1976.

Chandler, D. "The Sapir-Whorf Hypothesis" 2002, March, www.aber.ac.uk/media/Documents/short/whorf.html.

Chomsky, N. *Cartesian Linguistics: A Chapter in the History of Rationalist Thought* (third edition). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009.

Clark, E.V. *First Language Acquisition* (second edition). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009.

Diebold A.R. *Incipient bilingualism in Hymes: D.Ed. Language in Culture and Society*. New York, NY: Harper and Row, 1964.

Pinker, S. *The language Instinct*. England: Clays Ltd, 1994.

Powell, Barry B. *Writing: Theory and History of the Technology of Civilization*. Wiley-Blackwell, 2012.

Rossi-Landi, F. *Language As A Work & Trade*. Massachusetts: Bergin & Garvey Publishers, Inc.1983.

Weinreich U. *Language in Contact*. New York, New York: Linguistic Circle, 1953.